

Session report:

Understanding the UK dRTP Landscape

This session was run at the DRI Congress in Leeds in the Human DRI stream on 21 October 2025.

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Context

The goal of this session was to continue outlining the state of the digital Research Technical Professional (dRTP) landscape in the UK. It was the second event in the series (the first one was held at [RSECon25](#) in September) organised jointly by three dRTP skills NetworkPlus projects [CHARTED](#), SCALE-UP and [DisCouRSE](#). In order to create more entry points into and through a variety of dRTP roles, to improve the range of opportunities for professional growth, and to make these roles more attractive to individuals with diverse backgrounds, we need to start by understanding what the current dRTP landscape looks like. Only then we will be able to identify any gaps and develop strategies for making our community more sustainable.

Through a series of events we want to learn more about :

- dRTP Roles - what roles are included in the 'dRTP' scope? What are the key responsibilities? What are the progression pathways? How are they funded?
- dRTP Initiatives - what projects and initiatives work in this space? What are they focusing on? How do they fit into the wider landscape?
- dRTP Training - what training resources exist? What do they cover? Who owns them? Who can access it and how?

Our underlying goal is to better align training resources with skills, and skills with roles to make the dRTP ecosystem more transparent and easier to navigate for all stakeholders. The focus of this session was on dRTP roles.

Session Overview:

The session started with a brief introduction to the three NetworkPlus projects and their goals, followed by the motivation for organising a series of joint events and leveraging community contributions and feedback.

This was followed by an interactive mentimeter survey to better understand who was in the room and collected the participants' perceptions around dRTP roles, the overall landscape and known challenges. We spent about 35min on this survey - freely discussing both the questions and the results that were appearing on the screen.

The second part of the session was spent in a small group activity focused on contributing to the dRTP roles database. The attendees (23 participants and 3 presenters) split into 4 groups and independently worked in different tabs of the same spreadsheet to collect information about as many roles as the group members were familiar with.

The session was wrapped up with a general discussion summarizing both activities, followed by a very brief highlight of upcoming events.

Mentimeter results

The first question asked the attendees about their job title - most of them were in senior and leadership positions, ranging from Senior RSEs, Senior Policy managers and coordinators, to Professors, directors of Research Computing Services and Heads of Programmes. Fifteen attendees worked at Higher Education Institutions, five at Governmental Institutions, two at a non-profit organisation and other attendees indicated other places of employment. There were no representatives from Industry or the Commercial sector in the room. This distribution of the employment sector broadly aligned with the overall distribution of the Congress attendees - there were representatives from industry attending the Congress though.

The third question asked which of the listed role categories best aligned with the attendees' roles. Not surprisingly (given their job titles), ten indicated Institutional Leadership or Policy Making, six chose Project, Lab or Group Management, four selected Education and Training, and the remaining three were split between Infrastructure/Platform Engineering (two) and Software Engineering (one).

The next two questions included several statements related to people's perception of the overall landscape (Figure 1) and their own role (Figure 2). The attendees were asked to rate to what degree they agree with those statements from 1 to 5 (where strongly disagree =1 and strongly agree = 5). The general feeling was that there is a strong need for more people to work in the

dRTP roles to support digital research activities in the UK, and that the current progression pathways are not sufficient to support sustainable careers in dRTP roles (both scored 1.8). The next three statements received slightly higher overall scores, but the scores of 2.6 still indicate that the attendees did not think: dRTP careers are currently attractive to people from a wide range of experiences and backgrounds, there are enough opportunities for people in dRTP roles to connect with other community members, and there is sufficient access to training resources to improve existing or learn new skills.

The general feeling was that a lot more needs to be done to attract more people into dRTP roles, starting from more entry routes, to more recognition and more opportunities for career progression. It was noted that people have different motivations for going into dRTP roles.

To what degree do you agree with the following statements?

Figure 1 - A snapshot from the Mentimeter survey (Q4) run during the first part of the session. The attendees were asked about their overall perception of the dRTP landscape in the UK - the values on the Likert scale ranged from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Answers were aggregated from 23 participants.

When asked about their own roles, the attendees were a lot more positive in their answers. Everyone was fairly confident in understanding their role’s expectations (score of 4) and they also agreed they have most of the skills required for their role (score 3.7). The statement about possibility of personal development and career advancement also scored 3.7 but the answers were split across those that strongly agreed and those who slightly disagreed. The last two statements received mostly neutral answers: the score of 3.3 for ‘I know how to progress to the next career stage’ and 3.1 for ‘I have time and space to to concentrate on personal development

either dedicated or on-the-job'. This result could be a reflection of the participants' professional seniority.

To what degree do you agree with the following statements about your role?

Figure 2 - A snapshot from the Mentimeter survey (Q5) run during the first part of the session. The attendees were asked how they feel about their own role - the values on the Likert scale ranged from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Answers were aggregated from 23 participants.

The next two questions follow the same format but with the values on the Likert scale adjusted to Fully not aware - Fully aware range. Question six asked the participants to rate their awareness of roles (and the related skills) in the listed categories (identical to those listed previously for their role alignment question). The results are shown on Figure 3.

The averaged scores ranged from 3.2 to 3.7, so in the neutral to somewhat aware region, which was to be expected from the career stage and roles of people in the room.

The next question was very similar but re-focused on skills and training content and the listed categories were aligned with skill categories from the DIRECT framework (<https://directframework.com/>). The two categories that scored the highest at 3.7 were Software Engineering and Development, and Professional skills. The other categories scored from the lowest to the highest: Information and Data Technologies (2.8), Communication (2.9), Domain Expertise and Research (3.0), ICT Infrastructure (3.1) and Leadership and Management (3.3). It should be noted that the session leaders did not provide definitions and scope for each of the skills categories, though some clarifications were offered during the session. There was also a discussion on how to capture 'awareness of the lack of training for specific skills'.

How would you rate your awareness of roles and skills existing in the following spaces ?

Figure 3 - A snapshot from the Mentimeter survey (Q6) run during the first part of the session. The attendees were asked to rate their awareness of roles and skills across different categories. Answers were aggregated from 23 participants.

How would you rate your awareness of training and skills existing in the following areas?

Figure 4 - A snapshot from the Mentimeter survey (Q6) run during the first part of the session. The attendees were asked to rate their awareness of - the values on the Likert scale ranged from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Answers were aggregated from 23 participants.

The last three questions were open ended and focused on:

- The biggest challenges for creating and recruiting for dRTP roles,
- What can be done to better align skills with roles, and
- What is needed to improve the support for professional skills development for dRTP roles.

Some of the listed challenges included lack of sustainable funding, salary gaps compared to industry, lack of recognition in academic settings (second class citizens compared to ‘academics’), unclear or non-existent progression pathways, and push back from HR departments against creation of new roles.

The suggestions for improving the alignment between roles and skills covered three different layers of this complex problem:

- **Role definitions and Job families:** career matrix with well defined career pathway and progressions, agreement on minimum skillsets for different dRTP roles, recognition for ‘mixed roles’, mapping of roles at different institutions (as roles can vary depending on the size of the institution).
- **Skill frameworks** - map/equate skills to existing frameworks (e.g., Vitae RDF which many HEIs use), common skills frameworks that capture the relevant skills, appreciation that the skillset is a spectrum encompassing a variety of skills (at different levels).
- **Training resources:** training to lower the barrier to entry, more inclusive approach as the current system of luck and mentorships favours specific demographics, curated pathways along thematic dRTP roles, and very short courses that can be composed together to suit particular roles/personae.

Some of the provided answers sparked a lot of discussion around the benefits and dangers of job matrices and frameworks that are overly defined, too prescriptive and rigid. It was recognised that while some definitions and structures would be useful to help people discover and navigate different career options, those should be created carefully to ensure they will not be used to stop people with diverse backgrounds from entering into and progressing through dRTP roles. A rigid interpretation of any framework could limit people’s progression options, and narrow their career down to a single path. It was also suggested this could be avoided by including skill overlaps for different roles in such a framework to keep different progression pathways open for longer. The biggest challenge tends to be passing new roles through HR departments - the bigger the change the harder it is.

The suggestions for what can we do to better support people in dRTP roles were centred on the ideas of awareness and recognition, including parity of esteem for those in dRTP roles, recognition for software/data outputs to motive skill development across roles, recognition that training professionals are crucial to sustainable Digital Research Infrastructure, encouragement for institutions to allow dRTPs to attend skill development courses, and recognition that upskilling takes time and that personal development time needs to be factored into daily working life. Other discussion points included the need for more clarity on how to progress on different career pathways and what opportunities exist in other sectors (beyond HEI). The formation of a professional body was also mentioned. Finally, it was emphasized that the required cultural change needs to be an interactive process of developing, engaging and re-defining, to capture the needs of the dRTP community and reflect its growth.

Building dRTP Roles database activity

During the second half of this session the participants worked in groups to contribute to the dRTP Roles data set. They were asked to think of roles that are involved in support and delivery of digital research and for each role provide the following information (in the provided spreadsheet):

1. Name of Role
2. Description of Duties
3. How is it Funded (e.g. Baseline / Institutional Budget, 100% Recharged, Underwritten)
4. Category of Job (e.g. Software, Infrastructure, Data, Technical, Other)
5. Type of Job Family (e.g. Graduate-Level Only, 4 Levels Junior to Senior)
6. Progression Protocol (e.g. Vacancy-based, Promotion Checklist and Panel)
7. Example Organisation with this Role
8. Key Skills Required for the Current Role
9. Additional Skills Required for the Next Level Role

The dataset will be shared with the community after the series of events on “Understanding the UK dRTP landscape” concludes in spring 2026. It will collate the information collected during the sessions run at RSECon25, CIUK, and other events.

Discussions and Conclusions

Other comments that were captured during the session included:

- A gap in understanding of what training could or should be in the professional context - the understanding of what it means in academia is very different to that in industry.

- More effort could be put into understanding people’s motivation for taking specific training courses and see if there are any useful trends there.
- There is a lot of work being done in this space not only in the UK, but also in the EU. We should make sure to connect with relevant efforts.
- A single source of information about dRTP roles, related projects and training resources would make it easier for people to discover opportunities.
- Similar discussion should be held at a variety of events to engage with a broader community - not everyone in a dRTP role identifies as a digital Research Technical Professional. Community buy-in is necessary to affect the change.

Overall, the session generated a lot of discussion and allowed us to collect some useful data. This work was taken forward at a workshop held in London on 5-6 November, and will be continued with a similar session that will be run at [CIUK 2025](#).